

Prostate cancer dataset used for the classification phase of the Open Challenge

ID: 9737fc4b-8874-435e-b0dc-3e78f54ba22e

URL: <https://chameleon-eu.i3m.upv.es/dataset-service/datasets/9737fc4b-8874-435e-b0dc-3e78f54ba22e/details>

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Contact info.: <https://chameleon.eu/#contact>

Studies count: 433

Subjects count: 431

Age range: Between 46 years and 86 years

Sex: Male

Body part(s): PROSTATE, ARM, PELVIS, ABDOMEN, HEAD, PANCREAS, Unknown

Modality: MR